

Annex II

MAELSTROM Data access request form

Name and Surname:

Organization:

Project name and funding organization:

Contact Information:

Data requested:

How will the data be used? (please, provide as much information as possible concerning the purpose behind the data request and foreseen future publications)

Agree to MAELSTROM License Terms and Conditions

Date

Signature

To be sent to: fantina.madricardo@cnr.it; valentina.grande@cnr.it